

ISSUES OF USING SATELLITE TECHNOLOGIES IN MONITORING THE DEFORMATION OF RESERVOIR NODES

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Annotation. The main purpose of the article is to create a method of observation and analysis of the results obtained by using satellite monitoring methods of horizontal and vertical Silge of dams of water reservoirs in the Republic, scientific justification and application of this method in practice.

Keywords: dam, deformation, GPS, gidrotechnik, GNYT, satellite technology, GLONASS, NAVSTAR GPS, references, WGS-84.

Enter. Today, our country has many complex hydrotechnical structures, including water reservoirs, whose task is to supply agricultural and industrial needs with water and generate electricity. During the use of these structures, it is important to ensure their safe operation, that is, geodetic monitoring of their deformation.

The issue of optimal estimation of deformation parameters based on the results of geodetic measurements is of great importance. However, it is worth noting that today, increasing the effectiveness of determining the parameters of deformation using GPS technology allows to carry out positive targeted work at a sufficient level. Therefore, it was considered important and urgent to solve these cases using modern tools and methods.

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The main part. The supporting and fixing parts of hydraulic structures (hydroelectric power stations, dams) are weak from an engineering point of view and are often affected by water pressure. As a result of water pressure, natural influences and unstable foundations of structures, the device or its individual parts may undergo deformation (change). Excessive changes can damage structures and even cause their destruction. Therefore, it is important to observe and monitor hydrotechnical structures [1, 79-b].

The results of monitoring and evaluating the changes in structures, their stability and safety allow specialists to reliably and safely organize the process of construction of structures and their repair. Currently, the satellite tracking method is considered the most effective of these methods, because this method is distinguished from others by its accuracy, speed and ease of determining coordinate points.

The increased interest in the use of global navigation satellite systems (GNSS) in monitoring the change of engineering devices is explained by the accuracy, speed and level of automation of such systems.

In newly organized observations, satellite technologies can take the place of the main part of monitoring technologies based on the use of traditional geodetic tools (theodolite, level, etc.) [4, p. 86]. The disadvantages of traditional geodetic monitoring technologies, such as low work productivity, lack of automation of the work process, and the effect of weather on the work, can be eliminated on the basis of satellite technologies. Satellite technologies are free from such disadvantages.

The periodical performance of measurements during the period of use of the structure depends on the pattern of subsidence: it is carried out in a quarter of a year, half a year or in one cycle.

In order to solve the problems related to the effective use of modern satellite technologies in the monitoring of deformations in dams of hydroelectric power stations, the following tasks are studied (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. Scheme of application of modern technologies in monitoring deformations in dams

We can describe the scheme of using modern technologies in monitoring deformations in the mentioned dams as follows:

- the results of the value measurements of reservoir dams obtained on the basis of traditional methods and the analysis of the stability of the supporting points is carried out according to these results;
- the results of the measurements of water reservoir dams using modern methods, that is, based on satellite monitoring methods, and based on these results, the analysis of the stability of the base points is carried out;

- the horizontal displacement of reservoir dams is developed based on modern methods, i.e. satellite navigation measurement methods, and the results are analyzed;
- the coordinates of tracking marks are calculated by transferring them from the GPS satellite system to the flat system;
- the software for calculating the deformation values of reservoir dams is launched and high accuracy results are achieved.

Evaluation of monitoring results is one of the most difficult tasks for a geodesist. This is especially important in satellite technologies compared to the observation of angle, range and deviation by traditional methods, because in this method the observation technique itself does not appear as an overt physical factor. The surveyor should have dimensions based on complete equipment, and there should be no doubt that these equipment are working properly and they meet certain requirements [2, p. 96].

Reservoir dams are large and complex hydrotechnical structures, so their stability during use should be ensured. Otherwise, it can lead to big problems and even disasters. In order to ensure the stability of dams, it is important to determine the amount of subsidence and horizontal displacement by carrying out systematic geodetic observations. In this case, the main goal should be focused on ensuring the accuracy, reliability of the obtained results and quick execution of measurements.

The use of satellite technologies in the monitoring of dams allows independent assessment of deformations of hydrotechnical structures, controls traditional monitoring technologies, and allows detection of changes that cannot be detected using other technologies.

In conclusion, it can be said that scientific justification and practical implementation based on the modern method of analysis of the results obtained using satellite monitoring methods of the displacement and subsidence of dams will give positive results. The development of methods and results of deformation monitoring based on GPS technology, which allows to increase the reliability and efficiency of vertical and horizontal displacements based on the results of geodetic measurements, allows continuous monitoring of deformation.

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